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Use of Non-Standard Tests and its Significance in Verifying and Strengthening the Knowledge of School Students

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***Abstract:** This article describes methodical recommendations regarding the use of non-standard tests in checking the knowledge of schoolchildren and strengthening it.*

***Key words:** drawing, test, traditional test, non-standard test, knowledge, skill, assessment.*

The Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 5, 1993 "On admission of students to higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan by the test method" opened the way for the first use of the test in Uzbekistan among the CIS countries.

Through the use of graded tests in school drawing classes, students prepare graded test developments that can meet the needs of the times in order to strengthen and develop the acquired knowledge, teachers apply methodological recommendations in their pedagogical activities, and the school is sufficiently formed to strengthen theoretical and practical knowledge of students in the examination of students' knowledge. encourages them to find creative approaches and new ways of solving graphic tasks. Test (from the English "test" - test, check, study) is a test tool that allows determining the level of a certain condition in qualitative and quantitative indicators based on a specific goal. All tests, except for psychological tests, can be divided into the following three groups: tests that determine the level of intellectual development; pedagogical tests; tests that determine suitability for a particular profession.

The activities of pedagogues in the field of education have been observed, and their shortcomings in the assessment of students' knowledge are highlighted. Canceling the grade does not justify itself pedagogically and psychologically. Although the evaluation has a number of shortcomings, no alternative to the five-point evaluation system has been found. Therefore, it is necessary to improve it, not to make mistakes in the assessment of students' knowledge. In the examination of knowledge, the methods of taking into account the knowledge, skills and qualifications of students in drawing classes can be as follows: observing students in the work process; oral request; through testing; evaluation of

graphic works and homework notebooks; control work; solving problems; students' practical work (modelling, construction, etc.) and others.

A.A. Verbitsky offers a scientific basis for didactic tests used in the educational process. "In this case, the pedagogical test should serve to determine the student's knowledge and skills in the subject, not his professional training. Therefore, it is possible and necessary to determine the knowledge and skills of students with the help of a test. The quality of test results is improved by the following means: by increasing the number of test tasks; with the uniformity of understanding the essence of test tasks; ensuring uniformity of testing conditions. A traditional test consists of multiple-choice questions. Each question is evaluated for a certain point. The result of a traditional test is determined by the number of correctly answered tasks. There are the following types of traditional test: 1. A task to choose one correct answer. 2. Open tests. 3. Closed tests.

Non-standard tests are divided into the following groups according to their content and essence: 1. Integrative tests (tests of integrated content and form). 2. Adaptive tests (automated test). 3. Criteria-targeted tests (tests conducted to determine the general level of training of the learner). We can divide non-standard test forms into the following according to their content.

1. Non-standard test tasks used to control and evaluate the level of achievement of the learning goal of students.
2. Non-standard test tasks used to control and evaluate the level of achievement of the educational goal of students' understanding.
3. Non-standard test tasks used to control and evaluate the level of achievement of the educational goal of students' practical application of knowledge.
4. Non-standard test tasks used to control and evaluate the level of achievement of the educational goal of the students in relation to the analysis.
5. Non-standard test tasks used to control and evaluate the level of achievement of students' learning goal of knowledge synthesis.
6. Non-standard test tasks used to control and evaluate the level of achievement of the educational goal of drawing conclusions. Non-standard test - can be used for different tasks, tests with the same text. Non-standard test tasks with pictures and multiple answers allow to control not only the acquired knowledge of the students, but also the ability to identify the familiar and unique features of the object and its parts, and make it possible to carry out the evaluation process truthfully and fairly. Non-standard test tasks, examples of non-standard test used to control and evaluate the level of achievement of the educational goal of practical application of knowledge by students are given. For example, take Type 1 non-standardized testing: non-standardized test items used to monitor and evaluate students' achievement of cognitive learning objectives.

Condition of the test question: identify and write the numbers corresponding to the detailed views given in the picture.

The name of the types of shearing	Raqamlar
Profile cut	3
Frontal haircut	1
Combine half the look with half the cut	2
Horizontal cut	4

Or take the 2nd type of non-standardized testing: Non-standardized test items used to monitor and evaluate the level of achievement of the learning goal of students' understanding.

Test question condition: match the detail views with the properties on which projection plane they are made.

1.	Front view	A	Projection of detail is done in the plane of horizontal projections.		
2.	Top view	B	The projection of the detail is performed in the profile projection plane, for which the detail is viewed from the right side.		
3.	View from the left	C	The detail is viewed from its front and projected in the plane of frontal projections.		
4.	View from the right	D	The projection of the detail is performed in the profile projection plane.		
Answer:		1-	2-	3-	4-

The correct answer is:

Answer:	1-C	2-A	3-D	4-B
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At the same time, it cannot be said that the tests are completely free of flaws. Many forms of tests deprive the student of the experience of preparing answers independently. In these tests, the student's psychological activity differs from "free-form" answers, the student's individual aspects and intelligence are not shown. The person whose knowledge is being tested only chooses the correct answer. Checking students' knowledge with the help of tests and strengthening knowledge gives good results. However, it is not appropriate to use only the test method to determine and evaluate students'

knowledge of drawing geometry and drawing. The purposeful use of the test also leads to efficiency and quality in teaching.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, I can say that the school is designed to develop students' thinking ability and the ability to read a drawing in order to study the science of drawing more deeply. From this research work, by preparing graded test developments that can meet the requirements of the time, using electronic tests and methodological recommendations, teachers use them in their pedagogical activities, and by using graded tests in the drawing classes of their schoolchildren, they are directed to teach students in addition to checking and evaluating knowledge. by developing the possibility to find out the answers to the questions given by the test, the conclusions drawn in our research work, the fact that schoolchildren are sufficiently formed in strengthening theoretical and practical knowledge encourages them to seek a creative approach and new solutions in mastering the science of drawing, performing graphic tasks.

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